

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of β -Phenyl Propionic Acid by Peroxydisulphate Catalysed by Ag(I) Ion

G. L. MAHESHWARI, S. K. SINGHAL and B. D. TYAGI

Department of Chemistry, S. S. V. College, Hapur

Manuscript received 19 December 1974; revised 6 August 1975; accepted 8 August 1975

The kinetics of Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of β -phenyl propionic acid by peroxydisulphate in sulphuric acid (0.025M) medium has been investigated. The reaction was found to be of first order with respect to peroxydisulphate and Ag(I) ions and independent of the concentration of β -phenyl propionic acid. The salt effect was found to be negative. The sp. ionic effect is in order of $\text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$ and $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{H}^+$ for the ions of similar charges. However, the reaction is catalysed by $[\text{H}^+]$.

One mole of peroxydisulphate is found to react completely with one mole of β -phenyl propionic acid to give the mixture of phenyl acetaldehyde and benzaldehyde in the ratio of 87.5 : 12.5. The energy parameters are, $\Delta E = 22.05$ K.Cal/mole; $A = 3.86 \times 10^{10}$ litre/mole/sec. and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -10.18$ Eu.

The rate is inhibited by allyl acetate. The rate laws have been explained on the basis of a free radical mechanism involving Ag(II).

THE work on kinetic studies of oxidation of various organic and inorganic compounds by peroxydisulphate ion has been reviewed recently by House¹ and by Wilmerth and Haim². The oxidation of Carboxylic acids by peroxydisulphate ion in acid medium has been studied previously by a number of workers³⁻⁶.

In continuation of our study of the kinetics of oxidation of aromatic carboxylic acids and their related compounds by peroxydisulphate ion, a kinetic study of the Ag^+ catalysed oxidation of β -phenyl propionic acid was undertaken. The results of which are presented in this paper.

Materials and Methods

Hydrocinnamic acid (Extra pure, Fluka), Potassium peroxydisulphate (BDH AR.), silver nitrate (BDH AR.) were used. The rate of oxidation was followed by estimating the unreacted peroxydisulphate by the iodometric procedure of Kolthoff and Carr.⁷ To avoid precipitate formation, the reaction was carried out in sulphuric acid (0.025M) medium. The oxidation of hydrocinnamic acid gives a mixture of two compounds containing carbonyl group as the product of oxidation, which was estimated chromatographically.

Results and Discussion

The self decomposition of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ is appreciable under the experimental conditions employed, therefore, studied simultaneously and accounted for throughout these studies.

The results of the studies carried out at constant concentrations of β -phenyl propionic acid (0.0005M).

AgNO_3 (0.002M) and two different concentrations of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ (0.005 and 0.0075M) showed that equimolar concentrations of the reactants react to form a mixture of two compounds each containing carbonyl group.

The reaction follows first order behaviour w.r.t. $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ (as evidenced by linearity of the plots of $\log [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ vs. time), table 1. It is independent of the concentration of the reductant, table 2. Further,

TABLE I—EFFECT OF VARYING $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ ON THE RATE CONSTANT

Hydrocinnamic acid = $10^{-2}M$ $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2.5 \times 10^{-2}M$		Ag $\text{NO}_3 = 10^{-3}M$ Temp. 45°				
$[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \times 10^3$ (M)		5	10	15	20	25
$k = (k_2 - k_1) \times 10^3$ min. ^{-n'}		2.48	1.59	1.24	0.74	0.24

where k_2 = The sp. rate in presence of hydrocinnamic acid.
 k_1 = The sp. rate in absence of hydrocinnamic acid.
 k = The sp. rate of oxidation of hydrocinnamic acid.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING HYDROCINNAMIC ACID ON THE RATE CONSTANT

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 = 10^{-2}M$ $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 2.5 \times 10^{-2}M$		Ag $\text{NO}_3 = 10^{-3}M$ Temp. 45°				
$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}]$ $\times 10^3$ (M)		5	10	15	20	25
$k \times 10^3$ min. ⁻¹		1.72	1.59	1.59	1.59	1.59

the data summarized in table 3, exhibits that the rate of reaction increases linearly with $[Ag^+]_0$ according to the relationship.

$$k = 0.40 \times 10^{-3} + 1.20[Ag^+]$$

The data recorded in table 4 shows that the sp. rate decreases with the increase in ionic strength indicating a negative salt effect. However, the nature of the primary salt effect is not clear because neither a plot of $\log k$ vs $\mu^{1/2}$ nor, that of k vs μ is linear.

The sp. ionic effect of different cations on the sp. rate is in the order of

for the ions of similar charges (Table 5). However, H^+ have a catalytic effect, table 6, and the sp. rate of oxidation increases according to the relationship,

$$k = 0.12 \times 10^{-3} + 0.48 [H^+]$$

The reaction follows Arrhenius equation in the temperature range (308–328 °A) studied, and values

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING (Ag^+) ON RATE CONSTANT

$[Ag^+] \times 10^3 (M)$	Hydrocinnamic acid = $10^{-2}M$ Temp. 45°				
	$K_2S_2O_8 = 10^{-2}M$ $H_2SO_4 = 2.5 \times 10^{-2}M$	0.50	1.00	1.50	2.00
$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.20	1.59	2.20	2.80	3.40

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF ADDED SALT ON THE RATE CONSTANTS

Sl. No.	$[K_2SO_4] \times 10^3 (M)$	$K \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$-\log k$	Ag $NO_3 = 10^{-3}M$ Temp. 45°	
				μ	$\mu^{1/2}$
1.	0.00	1.80	2.7447	0.016	0.127
2.	0.50	1.48	2.8298	0.031	0.180
3.	1.00	1.31	2.8827	0.046	0.214
4.	1.50	0.88	3.0555	0.061	0.247
5.	2.00	0.50	3.3010	0.096	0.276
6.	3.00	0.38	3.4202	0.106	0.325

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF ADDED IONS

Added Salt	Ag $NO_3 = 10^{-3}M$ Temp. 45°				
	—	H_2SO_4 0.050M	$MgSO_4$ 0.0375M	$ZnSO_4$ 0.0375M	Na_2SO_4 0.050M
$k \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.80	0.05	1.65	0.61	0.39

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF (H^+)

$[H_2SO_4] (M)$	Ag $NO_3 = 10^{-3}M$, Temp. 45° Hydrocinnamic acid = $10^{-2}M$				
	$K_2S_2O_8 = 10^{-2}M$ $K_2SO_4 = 10^{-1}M$	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.004
$k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	0.24	0.32	0.42	0.55	0.66

of energy of activation, frequency factor, and entropy of activation are 22.05 K.Cal.mole⁻¹, 3.864×10^{10} litre, mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹, -10.18 Eu.

The reaction is greatly inhibited by allyl. acetate suggesting that the reaction follows a free radical chain mechanism.

Product analysis chromatographically

500 ml. of reaction mixture containing $K_2S_2O_8$ (5.40 g.) and hydrocinnamic acid (3.75 g.) catalysed by 0.002M $AgNO_3$ was kept at 45°; after 120 min. the mixture was ice cooled and shaken with 100 ml. of ether, and ether extract shaken with 5% aqueous solution of sodium bi-carbonate to separate unreacted hydrocinnamic acid.

The chromatographic glass plates (20" × 5") were coated to a thickness of 0.6 mm. by applicator. The plates were activated at 100° for 1 hr in an oven, plate was spotted with ether extract of the product, phenyl acetaldehyde and benzaldehyde as reference and developed in benzene containing 2% acetone for half an hour. The plate was dried and sprayed with 2:4 dinitrophenyl hydrazine solution. Red spots corresponding to phenyl acetaldehyde and benzaldehyde were obtained whose R_F values are reported below :

Compounds	R_F values
1. Reaction mixture	0.55, 0.65
2. Phenylacetaldehyde	0.55
3. Benzaldehyde	0.66

Thus it is seen that hydrocinnamic acid on oxidation yields the mixture of phenyl acetaldehyde and benzaldehyde.

Hydrocinnamic acid taken initially in the reaction mixture was 3.750 g. After the reaction was over, the unreacted substances were removed as above and the product obtained was found to be 2.987 g. after purification (about 53%). The two compounds present in the product were separated by semi-micro fractional distillation. The quantities of the two compounds obtained are given below :

Phenyl acetaldehyde	2.614 g. (87.5% approx.)
Benzaldehyde	0.373 g. (12.5% approx.)

Mechanism

Regarding the nature of silver species, the recent evidence in literature point out to the fact that in aqueous acid solutions, the existance of $Ag(II)$ is more likely than the higher state of silver species.

On the basis of above kinetic results and taking into consideration the previous data available, on the redox reaction on $S_2O_8^{2-}$, the rate expressions may be explained in terms of different free radicals. The mechanism up to the formation of phenyl

acetaldehyde which is major part of the reaction is as follows :

Applying the steady state treatment to different radicals, and assuming

$k \gg k_1$ and $k_2 \approx k_8$ and $[\text{Ag}^+]$ is very small,

$\frac{2k_1k_8}{k_2} [\text{Ag}^+] \ll k_7$ and may be neglected. Thus the rate of disappearances of $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ is

$\frac{[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = 3k_1[\text{Ag}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ which is the main feature of the reaction.

References

1. D. A. HOUSE, *Chem. Rev.* 1962, **62**, 185.
2. A. K. WILMERTH and M. HAIM, "Mechanism of Oxidation of Peroxydisulphate Ion, in Peroxide Reaction Mechanism", Ed. J. O. Edwards, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1962, p. 175.
3. U. S. MEHROTRA and S. P. MUSHRAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 41.
4. G. CHANDRA and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **11**, 773.
5. R. A. HERMENS and W. H. CONE, *Trans. Illinois State Acad. Sci.*, 1965, **58**, 144
6. S. P. SRIVASTAVA, G. L. MEHESHWARI and S. K. SINGHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 233.
7. I. M. KOLTHOFF, E. J. MEECHAN and E. M. CARR, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1953, **25**, 198.
8. I. M. KOLTHOFF, E. J. MEECHAN and E. M. CARR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **75**, 1439.